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DEPICTION OF THE IMAGE OF HUSEYN CAVID IN NAKHCHIVAN ARCHITECTURE

Abstract. Azerbaijani culture, art and architecture occupied a special place in the cultural life of the Near and Middle East due to the socio-economic and political conditions of the late 19th and early 20th centuries and the faster development of capitalist relations than in other Muslim Eastern countries. The study and promotion of Huseyn Javid's work, who lived and created at the same time and made unparalleled contributions to Azerbaijani culture, is an integral part of the state's cultural policy in Azerbaijan.

Even after the great leader Heydar Aliyev managed to return Javid's grave from Siberia to Baku in 1982, he did not spare the philosopher-poet his moral patronage and earned the poet his second acquittal. Later, the creation of Javid's House Museums in Nakhchivan and Baku, the construction of his mausoleum, the printing of his collection, and the holding of 100 and 120-year jubilee events are also connected with the name of the great leader Heydar Aliyev. Like Heydar Aliyev, during the reign of his visionary and wise follower – the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr Ilham Aliyev, a lot of work has been done in the field of elevating the name of Huseyn Javid, commemorating the writer's memory with respect and honor, and promoting Javid's creativity at the state level. The 125th, 130th, 135th and 140th anniversaries of Huseyn Javid were celebrated at a high level by the relevant decrees of the President Mr. Ilham Aliyev.

Key words: Nakhchivan, Huseyn Javid, mausoleum, theater, architecture.

Introduction. Huseyn Abdulla oglu Rasizade was born on October 24, 1882 in the spiritual family of Nakhchivan, one of the ancient centers of science, art and culture of Azerbaijan. Huseyin, who received his first

elementary education at home from his father, and then continued it in the religious school (mollakhana) between 1891 and 1896, studied at the Tarbiya school of the prominent enlightened intellectual and talented educator Muhammadtaghi Sidgi in 1896–1898, later, he was a permanent student of Tabriz “Talibiya” madrasa, which is considered one of the pedagogical centers of the region [4]. In 1909, the poet chose the literary pseudonym “Javid”, and later this name became the surname of both himself and his family.

The interpretation of the main material. The Nakhchivan theater, which was founded in 1882 and granted the status of a State Drama Theater in 1922, featured both romantic and realist works by world classics, as well as musical performances by talented actors and directors [6]. After the building was thoroughly renovated in 1923, the theater was named “Nakhchivan State Drama Theater”. In the 1920s and 1930s, the plays of H. Javidin and J. Jabbarli brought a new atmosphere to the theater’s repertoire, which developed mainly in a romantic and realistic styles.

The year 1937 left a black mark on the fate of Huseyn Javid, like many prominent intellectuals of Azerbaijan who were victims of repression. On June 3 of the same year, the great poet and dramatist was arrested on charges of being a “nationalist” against Javid, and on July 4, 1939, he was exiled to Siberia for his participation in anti-Soviet propaganda, and died on December 5, 1941 in Shevchenko settlement, Taishet district, Irkutsk region. On March 6, 1956, Huseyn Javid was acquitted by the judgment of the Supreme Court of the Azerbaijan SSR.

On the initiative of Heydar Aliyev, on October 26, 1982, the remains of the poet were brought from Siberia to Baku, and then to the city of Nakhchivan, where he was born and raised, and buried in front of his house. In 1981, a mausoleum was erected in the center of the city, reflecting the respect for Huseyn Javid. In 1996, a new mausoleum complex was built over Huseyn Javid’s grave.

Heydar Aliyev has always paid great attention and care to the personality, family, and heritage of Huseyn Javid, one of the prominent representatives of our literature. With his initiative and leadership, after the decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan on July 21, 1981 “On the 100th anniversary of the birth of Huseyn Javid”, the great poet and dramatist was highly appreciated at the state level, and the attitude towards the artist has changed radically. Based on this decision, several issues of state importance were resolved to perpetuate the memory of the poet.

In this decision, the creation of Huseyn Javid memorial museums in the cities of Baku and Nakhchivan, renovation of the facade of the house

No. 8, where Huseyn Javid lived from 1920 to 1937, on Istiglaliyet (former Communist) street of Baku, and the installation of a commemorative plaque of the writer were indicated in this decision [2].

The total area of the House museum in Baku, which consists of four rooms, is 245 m². There are 4,000 exhibits in the museum's main fund, and 200 in the scientific – auxiliary fund. The exposition includes more than 600 exhibits, including household and clothing items, Huseyn Javid's published books, programs and posters of stage plays, family and theater photos, a model of Huseyn Javid's mausoleum in Nakhchivan, paintings and other works of art dedicated to the poet, sheet music manuscripts of musical works composed by his son Ertogrul Javid, books used by him, paintings, gramophone shafts, letters and other documents are displayed. Many works of Huseyn Javid were prepared and published in Azerbaijani and many foreign languages by the house museum; A 30-volume "Javid studies" collection of studies reflecting materials on the life and work of Huseyn Javid was created, and books about the life and work of Ertogrul and Turan Javid were published [3].

Huseyn Javid's house-museum and memorial complex in Nakhchivan; On June 9, 1984, the museum created in the house in the Alikhan quarter, where the great Azerbaijani poet and playwright Huseyn Javidi was born, was opened. The museum, which has been operating as "Huseyn Javid's House-Museum" for a long time, has been named "Huseyn Javid's House-Museum and Memorial Complex" since 2015.

In 1981, one of the provisions of the decision of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan to celebrate the 100th anniversary of the genius poet and dramatist was the creation of the "Javid" Poetry Theater under the Nakhchivan State Musical Drama.

Fig. 1. The "Javid" Poetry Theater. During the grand opening ceremony of the building in October 1982.

Fig. 2. The Nakhchivan "Javid" Poetry Theater. 1982–1989.

“Javid” Poetry Theater operated during the years 1982–1989 and ceased operations in 1990. In 1981, the theater managed to stage this play for the first time on the stage of Nakhchivan, turning to the play “Sheyda” by the genius playwright. It is interesting that a few months after the premiere of that performance, the bureau of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan made a historic decision to celebrate Javid’s 100th anniversary. Based on this decision, thanks to Heydar Aliyev’s sensational initiative, decisive step and patronage in the then Soviet Union, on the evening of the day when H. Javid’s body, which was brought from distant Siberia, was laid to rest in the city of Nakhchivan - on November 6, 1982, with the play “My God is Beauty and Love” reflecting Javid’s life and creativity, the opening ceremony of the Poetry Theater took place (fig. 1,2).

A month before the grand opening, candidate member of the Political Bureau of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, First Secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Azerbaijan, and two-time Hero of Socialist Labor, Heydar Aliyev, made time to visit the “Javid” Poetry Theater during his visit to Nakhchivan. During this visit, he held a sincere half-hour meeting with the creative team of the Nakhchivan Theater [1].

A crowd of 80,000 people was waiting for private pensioner Heydar Aliyev, who returned to his native Nakhchivan 8 years after this incident, in front of the State Musical Drama Theater in Azadlig Square of the city.

On the evening of July 22, 1990, the great leader, who came to Nakhchivan to meet the people, visited the grave of Huseyn Javid near the Nakhchivan Theater. Addressing the public in front of the theater, Heydar Aliyev said: “The opening of the second state theater in Nakhchivan is a great cultural and historical event.” About a few months after that significant day, on September 1, the first season of the Nakhchivan State Puppet Theater, which was established in 1989 and started its operation in June 1990, was opened. Unfortunately, Heydar Aliyev, who was not in town as he was going to meet voters as a deputy candidate, could not attend the opening ceremony of the theater [1].

On October 23, 1992, Heydar Aliyev came to the Nakhchivan State Musical Drama Theater and took part in Huseyn Javid’s 110th anniversary party and gave a wide-ranging speech. On June 15, 1993, the historic return of Heydar Aliyev took place. In just 10 years, Azerbaijan became

a powerful state, it became known to the world as a country with a strong economy, brave army, flourishing science and culture. During these years, the theaters of Nakhchivan, like all the theaters of the republic, have developed. Their material and technical base has been improved, care for artisans has increased. Their dedicated work was duly appreciated. After Heydar Aliyev was elected the President of the country, like hundreds of artists of Azerbaijan, four actors of the ancient Nakhchivan Theater were awarded the title of People's Artist, and the main artist was awarded the honorary title of People's Artist, an actor was also awarded the Order of "Fame" [2].

The Huseyn Javid mausoleum, an architectural-commemorative complex built over the grave of the great Azerbaijani poet and playwright Huseyn Javid in Nakhchivan, was built on the personal initiative and patronage of the third president of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev. The author of the project of the monument is the honored architect of the Republic of Azerbaijan Rasim Aliyev, and the sculptor is the people's artist Omar Eldarov. The mausoleum was built by the "Star" Construction Company of the Republic of Turkey (Fig. 3.4).

The mausoleum consists of upper and lower – vault parts. For the mausoleum, in the area in front of the one-story house where Huseyn Javid once lived and which was turned into a museum, all the old buildings were demolished and the area was cleared, and according to the project of Rasim Aliyev, a small park was built in the south direction from the center of the Mausoleum towards Araz.

Fig. 3. Heydar Aliyev during the grand opening ceremony of the "Huseyn Javid" Mausoleum October 29, 1996. Nakhchivan

Fig. 4. Speech by the president of the "Star" company during the opening ceremony of the "Huseyn Javid" Mausoleum.

The architecture of the mausoleum was based on the traditions of Ajami Nakhchivani, the Nakhchivan school of architecture and the modern transcription of these traditions. The light of the star-shaped network ornaments fully illuminates the vault on the stylobate from the inside. The mausoleum is built of white marble. When you climb the stairs to the upper platform of the stylobate and enter the mausoleum, you can see a tomb, a tombstone and a chest stone under a glass cover on the lowest floor. Along the axis of the glass cover, there is a niche in which there is a white marble bust of Huseyn Javid, authored by Omar Eldarov (fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Architecture-commemorative complex erected over Huseyn Javid's grave.

The graves of Huseyn Javid's wife Mishkinaz Khanum and son Ertogrul are also in the mausoleum's crypt. On September 13, 1996, Heydar Aliyev accepted the request of the poet's daughter Turan and ordered to bring Mushkunaz's grave from Baku and Ertogrul Javid's grave from Nakhchivan to Javid's tomb. The opening of the monument took place on October 29, 1996, on the occasion of the 114th anniversary of Huseyn Javid's birth. The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Heydar Alirza oglu Aliyev, personally attended the opening of the mausoleum and made a speech. The grave of Huseyn Javid's daughter Turan Khanum is also in the crypt.

Fig. 6. Heydar Aliyev visiting the Nakhchivan "Javid" Poetry Theater. 1999.

Fig. 7. General view of the "Javid" Poetry Theater. 1999.

Conclusion. The attention and respect that Heydar Aliyev showed to Javid's creativity and personality is duly continued by the President of our country Mr. Ilham Aliyev (fig. 6,7). Thus, in 2022, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, signed the Decree on the celebration of the 140th anniversary of the poet-playwright's birth in our country, and the Action Plan was approved in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. After the restoration of Javid's house-museum and memorial complex, repair and restoration works were carried out on the tomb monument of the writer, which stands majestically in the city of Nakhchivan. The renovation works were carried out by the builders of the Nakhchivan City Department of the State Urban Planning and Architecture Committee of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic [5].

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Sevinc Tangudur (Azərbaycan)

NAXÇIVAN MEMARLIĞINDA

HÜSEYN CAVID OBRAZININ TƏRƏNNÜMÜ

Azərbaycan mədəniyyəti, incəsənəti və memarlığı, XIX əsrin sonu – XX əsrin əvvəllərində yaranan ictimai-iqtisadi, siyasi şərait sayəsində və kapitalist münasibətlərinin digər müsəlman Şərqi ölkələrinə nisbətən daha tez inkişaf etməsi səbəbindən, Yaxın və Orta Şərqi mədəni həyatında xüsusi yer tuturdu. Həmin dövrdə yaşamış və yaratmış Azərbaycan

mədəniyyətinə misilsiz tövhələr vermiş ədəbiyyatımızın korifey nümayəndələrindən biri olan Hüseyn Cavid yaradıcılığının tədqiq və təbliği Azərbaycanda dövlətin mədəniyyət siyasətinin ayrılmaz tərkib hissəsidir.

Açar sözlər: Naхçıvan, Hüseyn Cavid, məqbərə, teatr, memarlıq.

Севиндж Тангудур (Азербайджан)

ОБРАЗ ГУСЕЙНА ДЖАВИДА

В НАХЧЫВАНСКОЙ АРХИТЕКТУРЕ

Культура, искусство и архитектура Азербайджана заняли особое место в культурной жизни Ближнего и Среднего Востока в связи с социально-экономическими и политическими условиями конца XIX - начала XX веков и более быстрым развитием капиталистических отношений, чем в других мусульманских странах Востока. Исследование и пропаганда творчества Гусейна Джавида, одного из ярких представителей нашей литературы, жившего и внесшего беспрецедентный вклад в культуру Азербайджана, является неотъемлемой частью культурной политики государства в Азербайджане.

Ключевы е слова: Нахчыван, Гусейн Джавид, мавзолей, театр, архитектура.